

Physiological Functions of LMP2/ β 1i in the Female Reproductive System

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ABSTRACT

The ubiquitin proteasome system (UPS) is essential for many cellular processes, including the cell cycle, the regulation of gene expression and cell survival. Dysfunctional UPS can be associated with the underlying pathophysiology of specific diseases. The 20S proteasome core is composed of 28 subunits, which are arranged in four stacked rings, resulting in a barrel-shaped structure. The two end rings are each formed by seven α subunits, and the two central rings are each formed by seven β subunits. The over expression of LMP2/ β 1i in trophoblast cells of hydatidiform moles may contribute to its highly invasive phenotype. LMP2/ β 1i-deficient mice reportedly exhibit uterine neoplasms, with a disease prevalence of 36% by 12 months of age. Embryo implantation involves the invasion of placental extravillous trophoblast cells (EVTs) into the uterus. Normal human placentas or placentas from hydatidiform mole patients were collected and the expression of LMP2/ β 1i in different cell types including trophoblastic column (TC), cytotrophoblast cells (CTB) and syncytiotrophoblasts (STBs) was examined under different pathological states by pathological analysis. The expression of LMP2/ β 1i in TC of partial hydatidiform mole and complete hydatidiform mole placentas, was higher than that in TC of normal human placentas. Further the experiments with human and mouse uterine tissues clarified the physiological significance of LMP2/ β 1i in malignant myometrium transformation. In this mini review, we covered recent insights into the molecular pathways involved in LMP2/ β 1i-mediated physiological functions, with a particular focus on embryo implantation and uterine mesenchymal tumorigenesis.

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INTRODUCTION

The eukaryotic UPS is responsible for most aspects of regulatory and quality-control protein degradation in cells. Its substrates, which are usually modified by polymers of ubiquitin, are ultimately degraded by the immunoproteasome [1,2]. The ubiquitin-proteasome system (UPS) controls almost all basic cellular processes, such as progression through the cell cycle, signal transduction, cell death, immune responses, metabolism, protein quality control and development by degrading short-lived regulatory or structurally aberrant proteins [1,3,4]. Cytoplasmic proteins are mostly degraded by a protease complex, which has many substrates consisting of twenty-eight 20 to 30-kDa subunits, referred to as the immuno-

proteasome, and it plays key roll functions in the nucleus and cytoplasm of eukaryotic cells, while LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i individually appear to be more intense in the endoplasmic reticulum [5]. The proteasome structure is a cylindrical complex containing a core of four stacked rings around a central pore, with each ring being composed of seven individual proteins. The inner two rings are made of seven β subunits that contain three to seven protease active sites [6-10]. Two of the β subunits with an NH₂-terminal threonine residue, low molecular mass polypeptide (LMP) 2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i, which are induced by interferon (IFN)- γ , are encoded within the class II region of the MHC, directly adjacent to the transporter associated with antigen

presentation (TAP) 1 and TAP2 genes [11]. Several experiments have shown that IFN- γ -induced-incorporation of LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i into the 20S proteasome is responsible for antigen presentation [12,13]. Furthermore, the proteasome reconstructed by LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i, referred to as immuno-proteasome, produced increased chymotryptic and tryptic protease activities and modulated cleavage-site preferences of the proteasome [14-17]. Thus, immuno-proteasomes in different cells normally differ in subunit composition and functional activities in a way that correlates with the cell's capacity for antigen presentation [1]. This review shows that physiological functions of LMP2/ β 1i are important for maintaining embryo implantation and transforming mesenchymal cell in the female genital system.

Physiological significance of LMP2/ β 1i in embryo implantation

Implantation of the embryo into the uterine endometrium is a highly regulated event critical for the establishment of pregnancy. Successful embryo implantation depends upon the synchronized development of both the invasiveness of the embryo and receptivity of the endometrium [18]. This process is accompanied by extensive degradation and remodeling of the extracellular matrix (ECM). Numerous studies in mice, primates, and humans have shown that matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), which are responsible for degrading the ECM, are key regulators for blastocyst implantation [19-21]. Ubiquitin-related proteins were shown to be present in human, baboon, rhesus monkey, cow, sheep, and mouse pregnant uteri [22-26], and may be essential for endometrial modification and placental development during early pregnancy. However, no direct evidence has shown whether the UPS is involved in embryo implantation or has a regulatory effect on the activities of MMP-2 and MMP-9.

The expression levels of LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i significantly increased with the elongation of pregnancy. LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i mRNAs were mainly expressed in the luminal and glandular epithelia on Day 12 of pregnancy. On Days 18 and 26 of pregnant *Macaca mulatta*, strong signals of LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i mRNAs were detected in the placental villi, trophoblastic column, and arterial endothelial cells close to the implantation site, and moderate expressions were found in the trophoblastic shell and glandular epithelium (Fig. 1). LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i mRNAs were extensively distributed in the stroma on Day 26 of pregnancy. The expression patterns of LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i were like those of their transcripts, whereas weak immunostaining LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i were detected in stroma at all stages of pregnancy. LMP2/ β 1i and LMP7/ β 5i may be involved in placental villi invasion, degradation of ECM, immune tolerance, glandular secretion, and angiogenesis. The regulatory mechanism of LMP2/ β 1i on the expression and activities of MMP-2 and MMP-9 was examined using the human invasive extra villous trophoblast cell line, HTR8/Svneo. Although in LMP2/ β 1i-inhibited cells, the expression of mRNA encoding the nuclear factor kappa-B (NF- κ B)1 subunits, p105 and RelA/p65 remained normal, the 20S proteasome processes NF- κ B1 p105 into p50 is not observed [27]. In defective condition of LMP2/ β 1i, inactive NF- κ B1 results in defects in MMP-2 and MMP-9 activation.

Embryo implantation involves the invasion of placental extra villous trophoblast cells (EVTs) into the uterus. Hyperactive

EVT invasion occurs in hydatidiform moles and choriocarcinomas. Normal human placentas or placentas from hydatidiform mole patients were collected and the expression of LMP2/ β 1i in different cell types including trophoblastic column (TC), cytotrophoblast cells (CTB) and syncytiotrophoblasts (STB) was examined under different pathological states by immunohistochemical analysis. The expression of LMP2/ β 1i in TC of partial hydatidiform mole and complete hydatidiform mole placentas, was higher than that in TC of normal human placentas. The overexpression of LMP2/ β 1i in trophoblast cells of hydatidiform moles may contribute to its highly invasive phenotype (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. This picture shows implantation of the blastocyst, an early stage in embryo development, into the uterine epithelium. Cooperative interactions between trophoblast cells and maternal cells then form the placenta. In mammals, trophoblast cells lie adjacent to the surface epithelium of the uterus, but they do not invade it. Natural killer (NK) cells are also not present. Nutrients are transferred to the fetus from maternal blood vessels close to the uterine epithelium and in glandular secretions. This arrangement is known as an epitheliochorial placenta. The endometrium does not transform into the decidua, which is the name given to an endometrium that has differentiated under the influence of progesterone. In human placentation, trophoblast cells invade blood vessels as in rhesus macaques, but they replace the vascular endothelium in the myometrium to a greater degree. Invasion extends beyond the endometrium into the myometrium, whereas it is restricted to the endometrium in rhesus macaques. In addition, trophoblast cells invade the decidua, replacing the medial smooth muscle with fibrinoid material. Accompanying these changes is the presence of numerous NK cells. The expression of LMP2/ β 1i was observed in the placental villi, trophoblastic column, and arterial endothelial cells close to the implantation site, and the moderate expression of LMP2/ β 1i was found in the trophoblastic shell and glandular epithelium. LMP2/ β 1i expression in trophoblast cells of hydatidiform moles may contribute to its highly invasive phenotype.

Physiological role of LMP2/ β 1i in uterine mesenchymal tumorigenesis

UPS is essential physiological function for many cellular processes, including the cell cycle, regulation of gene expression, cell survival and immunological functions. The individual expression of LMP2/ β 1i, LMP7/ β 5i, and LMP10(MECL-1)/ β 2i subunits is believed to contribute to the initiation and development of disorders including tumorigenesis [27-29]. A recent study revealed a unique role

for LMP7/ β 5i in controlling pathogenic immune responses and provided a therapeutic rationale for targeting LMP7/ β 5i in autoimmune disorders, especially rheumatoid arthritis (RA) [30]. In mouse models of RA, a LMP7/ β 5i-inhibitory treatment reversed the signs of disease and resulted in reductions in cellular infiltration, cytokine production, and autoantibody levels. Homozygous mice deficient in LMP2/ β 1i exhibit tissue- and substrate-dependent abnormalities in the physiological functions of UPS [31,32]. Uterine leiomyosarcoma (uLMS) reportedly occurred in female LMP2/ β 1i-deficient mice at the age of 6 months or older, and the incidence at 14 months of age was about 37% [32-34]. Disease prevalence in mice is similar to that of human uLMS, which occurs after menopause. Histological studies of LMP2/ β 1i-deficient uterine tumors revealed the characteristic abnormalities of human uLMS [32]. Recent reports have demonstrated that LMP2/ β 1i is obligatory for tumor surveillance and the tissue-specific role of LMP2/ β 1i in protection from spontaneous uterus neoplasms [31,32]. The nuclei of tumor cells varied in size and shape; furthermore, mitosis is frequently observed. The tumors lacked lymphoid infiltrates, a sign of immune-recognition, and consisted of uniformly elongated myometrium cells arranged into bundles. The nuclei of tumor cells varied in size and shape. In contrast, the myometrium cells of C57BL/6 mice were normal in appearance [32]. Whereas relatively few ki-67-positive cells, which are proliferating cells, were observed in the basal cell layer of the normal myometrium, most of the basal cells in LMP2/ β 1i-deficient mice strongly expressed ki-67 [32]. This immunological staining indicates the abnormal proliferation of LMP2/ β 1i-lacking cells in the basal layer. Although the immunoproteasome from LMP7/ β 5i knock out mice showed altered proteolytic activities and cleavage site preferences, no report has shown that LMP7/ β 5i knock out mice exhibit uterine neoplasms [35]. Therefore complex of molecule of LMP2/ β 1i with cellular cofactor(s), neither than physiological function of immunoproteasome, likely prevents initiation of uterine mesenchymal tumor [36,37].

Furthermore, immune-staining experiments revealed a serious loss in the ability to induce LMP2/ β 1i expression in human uLMS tissue relative to that in leiomyoma (LMA) or a normal myometrium located in the same section [36,37]. Of the 54 cases we examined with human uLMS, 46 were negative for LMP2/ β 1i expression, 4 were focally positive, and 2 were partially positive [37]. In two uLMS cases, expression levels of LMP2/ β 1i were also evaluated in skeletal muscle and rectum metastases from individual patients with uLMS [37,38]. All lymph nodes were negative for human uLMS metastases, and IHC studies showed positivity for ki-67 and negativity for LMP2/ β 1i [37-39]. UPS regulates the turnover and functions of hundreds of cellular proteins in uterine tumorigenesis [40].

Final Consideration

In conclusion, LMP2/ β 1i was highly overexpressed in trophoblast cells of hydatidiform moles, and expression of LMP2/ β 1i in aggressive EVT cells directly regulated cell invasion. Human uLMS is refractory to chemotherapy and has a poor prognosis. Defective expression of LMP2/ β 1i may be one of the risk factors for the development of human uLMS-like neoplasm. The physiological functions of LMP2/ β 1i with cellular cofactor(s) are important to maintain embryo implantation and the transformation of mesenchymal cells in the female reproductive system.

Conflict of interest

All authors report no conflict of interest.

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